

Extinction risks of frogs under climate change

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Project Objectives

Global climate change poses major threats to biodiversity (Thomas *et al.*, 2004). A potential weakness of previous studies that project biodiversity impacts of climate change is their reliance on correlative bioclimatic habitat models that do not consider species life history. Important advances that overcome this limitation are: coupled species modelling approaches that integrate stochastic population models with bioclimatic habitat models (Keith *et al.*, 2008); and mechanistic habitat models based on physiological budgets of energy and water (Kearney *et al.*, 2010). These approaches combine complementary strengths of the component models (mechanistic realism, broad generality).

This working group brought together ecological modellers, biologists and managers to apply these new approaches to Australian frog species. Frog populations have undergone serious declines in recent decades and a third of species are now listed as threatened worldwide, with current extinction rates estimated to be > 200 times the background rate (Stuart *et al.*, 2004). Eastern Australia has been identified as a global hotspot of frog decline (Campbell, 1999). Frogs are a priority for study because they are a functionally important group with critical dependence on climatic moisture. In addition, they are exposed to diverse threats, including habitat loss, disease, predation and wetland degradation, which are likely to interact with climate change in complex ways.

Our objectives were to:

- (i) produce reliable projections using the most recent frog population and climate data with state-of-the-art modelling approaches;
- (ii) explore the sensitivity of risk assessment protocols to threats posed by climate change;
- (iii) identify life history characteristics that predispose certain frogs species to climate change impacts;
- (iv) assess the influence of habitat connectivity and dispersal on climate change impacts; and
- (v) examine interactions between climate change and other threats such as fire and disease.

Methods

For 14 Australian frog species, we developed habitat suitability models, projected them spatially into the future using regionally skilled General Circulation Models and, using an approach described by Keith *et al.* (2008), coupled them with detailed stochastic population models reflecting expert knowledge and available data on species life history. The frog species represented a range of body sizes, reproductive types, habitat dependencies and range sizes. For a subset of species, we also developed biophysical models based on available data for energy and water budgets of the animals. We used the models to simulate realistic scenarios of population dynamics under future climates. We simulated additional scenarios to explore effects of connectivity and disturbance management options.

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Major Findings

The distributions of all frog species were projected to decline under future climates except in Tasmania (Table 1). The magnitude and spatial pattern of decline varied between species. Coupled models projected population declines in all species (including in Tasmania, Table 1). Uncertainty in climate projections did not influence this conclusion. Two species were projected to go extinct under the most extreme scenario. For one species studied in detail (*Asa darlingtoni*), IUCN Red List criteria indicated threatened status at least 40-80 years before extinction occurred, indicating that such risk assessments may be useful for detecting risks posed by climate change. Simulations showed that enhanced habitat connectivity reduced extinction risks in one species, but did not reduce risks appreciably in four others (Figure 1). The species most sensitive to connectivity (*Helioporus australiacus*) had the greatest ability to disperse of those studied. Preliminary investigations of management scenarios for that species suggest that declines under climate change could be slowed by appropriate fire management. Extinction risks under future climate change were lowest when fire intervals are longer than 30 years and highest when intense fire occurs at intervals of less than 10 years.

Table 1. Projected changes in habitat suitability and population viability (Effective Minimum Abundance) for selected Australian frog species based on CSIRO Mark 3 Global Circulation Model (GCM) under the A1FI emissions scenario (IPCC 2007).

Species	Projected Habitat Suitability in 2100 (% 1990 value)	Effective Minimum Abundance (% initial abundance)
<i>Asa darlingtoni</i>	0	0
<i>Crinia nimbus</i>	in progress	in progress
<i>Geocrinia victoriana</i>	7	2
<i>Heleioporus albopunctatus</i>	18	17
<i>Heleioporus australiacus</i>	17	8
<i>Litoria aurea</i>	in progress	in progress
<i>Litoria booroolongensis</i>	in progress	in progress
<i>Litoria raniformis</i> (Mainland)	34	26
<i>Litoria raniformis</i> (Tasmania)	176	79
<i>Litoria spenceri</i>	15	14
<i>Philoria frosti</i>	0	0
<i>Pseudophryne bibroni</i> (Mainland)	9	10
<i>Pseudophryne bibroni</i> (Tasmania)	125	87
<i>Pseudophryne pengilleyi</i>	1	3

Figure 1: Population viability (Effective Minimum Abundance as a fraction of initial abundance) of five Australian frog species under climate change (projected by CSIRO Mark 3 GCM, A1FI emissions scenario) and three different levels of habitat connectivity representing different landscape management strategies.

How will this affect Australian ecosystem science & management?

Our studies show that empirical population data and life history knowledge can be coupled with traditional correlative distribution models to strengthen predictions of biodiversity impacts from climate change. Preliminary evaluations suggest that current risk assessment methods, such as the IUCN Red List criteria for threatened species may be sufficient to detect species at risk from climate change with sufficient lead time for adaptation actions. Our models suggest that management of other threatening processes will be crucial to species persistence under future climates. In particular, manipulation of landscape connectivity may reduce extinction risks in some frog species, while manipulation of fire regimes may reduce risks to others under future climates.

Key papers or products

Keith, D. A., Mahony, M., Hines, H., Elith, J., Regan, T. J., Baungartner, J. B., Hunter, D., Heard, G. W., Mitchell, N. J., Parris, K. M., Penman, T., Scheele, B., Simpson, C. C., Tingley, R., Tracy, C. R., West, M. Akcakaya, H. R. (in review). How soon can the IUCN Red List criteria of Threatened Species detect risks posed by anthropogenic climate change? *Conservation Biology*.

Additional manuscripts are in preparation on: biophysical models of frog distribution; species trait patterns in extinction risk of frogs; chytrid and its impact on frog populations; translocation as a climate adaptation for montane frogs.

Presentations

Penman, T. Mahony, M., Elith, J., Keith, D., Regan, T. (2013). Climate change, fire and one giant frog. *Australian Society of Herpetologists Conference*, Lake Macquarie.

Regan, T. J. (2013). The role of connectivity when managing for species persistence under climate change. *INTECOL Conference*, London.

References

Campbell, A. (1999). *Declines and Disappearances of Australian Frogs*. Environment Australia, Canberra.

IPCC 2007. Fourth Assessment Report.

Kearney, M. R., Wintle, B. A. and Porter, W. P. (2010). Correlative and mechanistic models of species distribution provide congruent forecasts under climate change. *Conservation Letters* 3:203-213.

Keith, D. A., Akçakaya, H.R., Thuiller W., Midgley, G.F., Pearson, R.G., Phillips, S. J, Regan, H.M., Araujo, M.B. and Rebelo, T.G. (2008). Predicting extinction risks under climate change: coupling stochastic population models with dynamic bioclimatic habitat models. *Biology Letters* 4:560-563.

Stuart, S.N., Chanson, J.S., Cox, N.A., Young, B.E., Rodrigues, A.S.L., Fischman, D.L. and Waller, R.W. (2004). Status and Trends of Amphibian Declines and Extinctions Worldwide. *Science* 306:1783-1786.

Thomas, C. D., Cameron, A., Green, R.E., Bakkenes, M., Beaumont, L.J., Collingham, Y.C., Erasmus, B.F.N., Ferreira se Siqueria, M., Grainger, A., Hannah, L., Hughes, L., Huntley, B., van Jaesveld, A.S., Midgley, G.F., Miles, L., Ortega-Huerta, M.A., Peterson, A.T., Phillips, O.L. and Williams, S.E. (2004). Extinction risk from climate change. *Nature* 427:145-148.

The group is developing a series of animations of predicted distribution change in Australian frogs.

An example of the distribution for *Litoria raniformis* is shown on the [ACEAS web site](#).

Grid colour ramp (to which the legend corresponds): Habitat suitability at a 9975 x 9975 m pixel. This grid is the result of aggregating (summing) each 35 x 35 cell block of 285 x 285 m cells, each of which had a habitat suitability score of between 0 and 1. The cells shown here therefore have a theoretical maximum of 1225 (35 x 35).

Points: These indicate centroids of occupied patches of suitable habitat. The colour of points indicates their mean simulated population size at a given timestep, and ranges from white (abundance = 1 female) to black (abundance = maximum observed across timesteps and populations). **Grey grid pixels** indicate the IBRA regions from which the Maxent background sample was drawn.

Litoria raniformis (Kerferstein, 1867)
Common names: Growling Grass Frog,
Southern Bell Frog. (photo: Geoff Heard)